

Research Paper

Role of Various Educational Commissions, Committees and Different Aspects Regarding Teacher Education in 20th Century of India

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ABSTRACT

A rich tradition of teacher education was founded in India for historical reasons. During 20th century many educational commissions, committees, and schemes were established by the Government of India for the development of teacher education. The Government of India realised the importance of teacher education as a result of which many reforms were brought out particularly in the 20th century. Many commissions, committees, and schemes were set up for strengthening the system of teacher education, and its nature, importance, challenges were access during that time. The commissions, committees have pointed out several recommendations and suggestions still prevailing in the teacher education system in India. Therefore, there was an urgent need to rectify in order to develop quality and competence among prospective teachers, so that they may be able to fulfil their changed roles and responsibilities effectively and successfully. In this study the authors tried to highlight the various educational commissions, committees, and schemes regarding teacher education in the 20th century in India and also in West Bengal. The authors also tried to shed some light to the relevance that the aspects like nature, importance, challenges, and some suggestions for the challenges of teacher education.

Keywords: Educational Commissions, Educational Committees, Schemes, Teacher Education in the 20th Century

Teaching is one of the oldest and highly respected careers worldwide. The great work of educating the citizens of the future is done by the teachers. The expectations of society accelerate the pace of the teaching process. Teacher education refers to the correct policy and decision making by adapting to the classroom, school, and society with the knowledge, skill, attitude, behaviour etc. required for the environment (Singh & Sharma, 1995). Teachers need to develop appropriate knowledge and skills in teaching, evaluation, and practice of those standards and appropriate standards (Desai, 2012). The Good's dictionary of education stated that teacher education is defined as all the formal and non-formal activities and experiences that enable a person to qualify as a member of the teaching

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profession. The education commissions, committees, schemes, programmes, and other activities recommend the introduction of a “sound programme of professional education of teachers”. During the preparation of teachers, there had been a dramatic change in the dynamic society from time to time, with all the influencers being the importance, challenges of education, the role, nature, and skills, but the need for teachers to change this society forever (Martin, 1994). Keeping in mind the needs of the society, the process of teacher preparation should be modernised, and appropriate implementation. This paper elaborated the role of educational commissions and committees regarding teacher education in the 20th century of India.

Background of the Study

The main aim of education in ancient India was to persuade the teacher educator to self-achievement by combining spiritual knowledge with mundane and practical knowledge, and the teacher of ancient India was proficient in spiritual knowledge as well as practical knowledge. In the medieval ages, imparting knowledge to students was one of the tasks of teachers (Gupta, 1999). However, in the 20th century most teachers acted as interpreters of knowledge. With the change in the role, importance, and functions of the teacher came the change in the concept and time of teacher education. Education is not exotic (borrowed from outside) in India. India was known as the most enlightened country in history. In addition to the history of Indian education, the history of teacher education in India was very ancient (Dixit, 2014). From the presence of teachers and students in the ancient society proper ideas of the educational system of that era can be found. Introducing teacher education with the general education system is quite flexible and successful. Teachers’ educational system may be taken as born in 2500 B.C. as education itself. The history of education in India can be divided into five distinct periods:

1. Ancient and medieval period: 2500 B.C. to 500 B.C.
2. Buddhist period: 500 B.C. to 1200 A.D.
3. Muslim period: 1200 A.D. to 1700 A.D.
4. British period: 1700 A.D. to 1947 A.D.
5. Post-independence period: 1947 up to the date.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were:

- O₁: To study the development of teacher education in India and West Bengal in the 20th century by the recommendations of different educational commissions, committees, schemes, programmes, and activities.
- O₂: To establish the relation between various aspects of teacher education in the 20th century of India.

Research Questions of the Study

The aim of this study was to address the research questions outlined here:

- RQ₁: What is the development of teacher education in India and West Bengal in the 20th century by the recommendations of different educational commissions, committees, schemes, programmes, and activities?

RQ₂: How to establish the relation between various aspects of teacher education in the 20th century of India?

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The study was purely historical research in nature which was based on qualitative work. Books written on teacher education in India during 20th century used as secondary sources. This study was purely theoretical based. Content analysis was done on the available documents. The investigators were collected data from different types of books, web portals, journals (including e-journals), and articles written by the great authors.

Delimitations of the Study

The delimitations of the study were:

- The present study was delimited to the teacher education of India in the 20th century.
- The study was also delimited to the recommendations of various commissions, committees, schemes, programmes, and activities regarding teacher education in India and West Bengal.

Analyses of the Study

Analysis of O₁: To study the development of teacher education in India and West Bengal in the 20th century by the recommendations of different educational commissions, committees, schemes, programmes, and activities.

- **RQ₁**: What is the development of teacher education in India and West Bengal in the 20th century by the recommendations of different educational commissions, committees, schemes, programmes, and activities?

The Indian Universities Commission (1904): The educational policy published on March, 1904 by Lord Curzon. Subject specialised and proper trained teachers' recruitment in teacher training colleges or normal schools. The duration of training courses of graduate and pre-graduate candidates for 1 year and 2 years respectively, affiliated by the universities (Mangal, 2020).

The Government of India Resolution on Education Policy (1904): Lord Curzon, then the viceroy of India felt that need of the training of teachers. It made some vital suggestions for the improvement of the teacher training programmes (Singh, 1990). These were:

- ***Training Colleges***: The resolution stated that teachers need to be trained in the teaching strategy and more organised to emphasise and enhance secondary education. There were five teachers' training colleges in all at places like Madras, Kurseong, Allahabad, Lahore, and Jubbulpore (Mangal, 2020).
- ***Training Schools***: The resolution recommended opening of more training schools, particularly in Bengal, and a minimum teacher training course of 2 years. Rural school teachers were mentioned in the integrated training courses. Universities instituted B.T. degree for graduate teachers.

The Government of India Resolution on Education Policy (1913): The second resolution emphasised that no teacher should be allowed to teach without a certificate and that there should be a constant exchange of ideas amongst the training colleges' staff members and that they should visit different colleges (Sharma, 2013).

The Calcutta University Commission/Sadler Commission (1917-1919): This commission suggested that the training programme should not only make the trainee a competent classroom teacher but also a good administrator. The recommendations of the Sadler

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Commission had a beneficial effect on teacher training programmes in India. Mysore University started a faculty of education in 1925 (Mohanty, 2003).

The Hartog Committee (1929): The committee rightly observed that the success of education depended on the quality of the training, the status, and the pay of teachers. The proposal recommends that teachers for rural areas should be selected from among individuals who have strong connections with rural communities (Bhatia, Kaur, & Singh, 2024). It also added that the period of training was too short, the curriculum too narrow and the teaching staff inadequately qualified, and the journals for teachers in the vernacular, refresher courses, conferences, and meetings of teacher associations can do much to brighten the lines of the teachers and improve their work (Dodiya, 2018).

The Abbot-Wood Report (1937): According to the report, the duration of training should be 3 years to enable the trainees to continue with general education along with professional training. It further suggested a refresher course for the teacher so that he could get a wider experience. Although there was improvement in the percentage of trained teachers from 56.8% in 1937 to 61.3% in 1942 (Singh & Sharma, 1995).

Zakir Hussain Committee Report (1937): The committee submitted its report on 2nd December, 1937 and the scheme of education suggested by its popularly known as the 'Wardha Scheme' (Dodiya, 2018). The plan is designed to make teachers financially independent enough to cover salaries and aims to ensure that students can support themselves after completing their courses (Kumar & Vashisth, 2014).

The Sargent Report (1944): In 1944, the Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE) presented a scheme of education "Post war Educational Development in India", popularly known as 'Sargent Plan'. Recommendations were to enrol qualified youth in the teaching profession after completing high school, provide them with hands-on training, organise refresher courses and provide research facilities. (Singh, 1990). It suggested a 2 years course for pre-primary and junior basic schools (after high school) and a 3 years course for the senior basic schools. The non-graduate teachers in high schools were to go for 2 years training and the graduates for 1 year training. It proposed revised pay scales for all categories of teachers, to attract better teachers (Sharma, 2013).

The University Education Commission (1948-1949): The first commission in free India constituted under the chairmanship of Dr. S. Radhakrishnan. The Commission noted that although the theory courses offered in various teacher training colleges were similar, there were significant differences in the practices implemented, and recommended for remodelling of teachers' training programmes giving more time to school practices, and more weight to practice in assessing learners' performance.

Indian Association of Teacher Educators (IATE, 1950): IATE, formerly known as All India Association of Training Colleges, the only national organisation of teachers' training institutions, had been organising annual conferences beginning with their initial encounter in 1950 in Baroda (Mangal, 2020). It constituted a study group to revive B.Ed., commonly known as the Baroda Study Group.

The Secondary Education Commission (1952-1953): Under the chairmanship of Dr. A. Lakshmanswami Mudaliar, the commission recommended dynamic methods for teaching and suggested that the teaching should be shifted from verbalism and memorisation to

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learning through ‘activity method’ and ‘project method’, and during 1 year of training graduate teacher should be trained in methods of teaching in at least two subjects. It made specific guide lines for the teacher preparation also (Kumar & Vashisth, 2014).

Ford Foundation Team (1954): Government of India in collaboration with Ford Foundation appointed an international team of 8 experts that studied in greater detail the major recommendations of training institutions should organise and conduct demonstration or laboratory schools where experiments were made in curriculum construction and progressive methods of teaching were used (Singh & Sharma, 1995).

Pires Committee (1956): Under the chairmanship of Dr. E. A. Pires, recommended that the reconstruction of secondary level teachers’ training course’s syllabus and the practical work should be given as much weight age as the theory portion. It was also suggested that the methods of teaching are done by two school subjects (Singh, 1990).

Establishment of National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT, 1961) and Regional Colleges of Education (RCE, 1963): The NCERT was set up in 1961, merging Central Institute of Education (CIE) and the RCE (Mysore, Ajmer, Bhopal, Bhubaneswar, and Shillong) was established under the auspices of NCERT in 1963 (NCTE, 1998). It recommended integrating professional and general programmes by organising content-cum-pedagogy courses of 4 years duration (Singh, 1990).

The Education Commission (1964-1966): It was set up by the Government of India under the chairmanship of Dr. D. S. Kothari. It noted that a strong programme of professional development of teachers is crucial to raise the quality of education at all levels to meet the needs of the national education system. It suggested ways to improve the quality of teacher educators and advised the State Governments to prepare a plan for the expansion of training facilities (Martin, 1994).

The National Policy on Education (NPE, 1968): The policy made recommendations regarding the service conditions of teachers, academic freedom of teachers, and in- service education. Teacher, must therefore, be accorded an honoured place in society (Singh & Sharma, 1995).

The Planning Commission in the Fourth Five Year Plan (1969-1974): It emphasised on teacher education for improving its quality, training more women teachers, and teachers from tribal communities, training science, and mathematics teachers for the middle class and organising in-services training. It recommended correspondence courses for the training of teachers’ already in-service and training programmes for teacher educators (Sharma, 2004).

First Asian Conference on Teacher Education (1971): This conference jointly sponsored by Indian Association of Teacher Educators (IATE) and the International Council on Education for Teaching (ICET) was held at Bangalore. It recommended that the programmes of teacher education in each country should be modified to meet the new challenges (Bhatia et al., 2024).

Establishment of National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE, 1973): The ministry of Education Government of India established the NCTE in 1973, to maintain the standard of

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teacher education in the country; NCTE struggled to function effectively till 1993, when it got statutory status as a national apex body. The functions of NCTE are (NCTE, 1998):

1. To survey the whole field of teacher education at all levels and suggests ways and means of improvement of the same.
2. To suggest proposals to central ministry for planned development of standards of teacher education in the country (Sharma, 2013).
3. To plan the sponsor in-service training programmes and maintains international contacts in the field of teacher education (Mohanti, 2003).

De Committee (1978) and Himanshu Bimal Mazumdar Committee (1978): It emphasised on quality improvement, good management as well as teacher recruitment, infrastructural development etc.

Establishment of State Council of Educational Research and Training (SCERT, 1980): One of the major functions of this council is the control and supervision of elementary teachers' training programmes by Government of West Bengal (Martin, 1994).

National Commission on Teachers/The Chattopadhyaya Committee (1983-1985): This commission appointed by the Government of India in 1983 under the chairmanship of professor D. P. Chattopadhyaya, recommended that the selection of trainees should be made through a combination of objective tests, rating scales, group discussions, and personal interviews (Mandal, Behera, Bhowmik, & Biswas, 2017).

Bhabatosh Dutta Committee (1984): Bhabatosh Dutta was a great economist in West Bengal. The Government of West Bengal had established an education committee under the chairmanship of Bhabatosh Dutta. It suggested that trained teacher recruitment and qualitative improvement of teacher education (Mandal, Behera, Bhowmik, & Biswas, 2017).

The National Policy on Education (NPE, 1986): It recommended that teacher education is a continuous process and its pre-service and in-service components are inseparable made a strong case for improving the quality of teacher education because it was the pre-requisite to improve the quality of school education (Mohanti, 2003).

Establishment of District Institutes for Educational Training (DIET, 1987): DIET served as pre-service and in-service training institute for teachers in the district and competence of teachers through regular training programmes, projects, seminars, workshops, and other academic programmes (Kumar & Vashisth, 2014).

Pabitra Sarkar Committee (1988): Professor Pabitra Sarkar was Ex. Vice Chancellor of Rabindra Bharati University and Ex. Chairman of West Bengal State Council of Higher Education. It emphasised on quality improvement and good management as well as teacher recruitment, revision of curriculum, regular inspection, infrastructural development etc. (Mandal et al., 2017).

The Acharya Ramamurti Review Committee (1990): It recommended that in-service and refresher courses should be related to the specific needs of teachers, and that evaluation and follow-up should be part of the scheme.

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Ashok Mitra Commission (1991-1992): Under the chairmanship of Ashok Mitra, the commission recommended that teacher should be graduate, trained teachers are desirable, total teaching day's may not be less than 220 days, and private tuition should be strictly prohibited. As per recommendations of this commission in West Bengal, that every secondary teacher should be appointed by the school service board (known as now West Bengal Central School Service Commission) (Mandal et al., 2017).

Programme of Action (POA, 1992): POA was the reflection and reconstruction of NPE, 1986. It had very wide terms and reference right from the objectives for teaching profession to the National Foundation for Teachers' Welfare (NFTW). It engaged with different segments of the population and gathered their views on how to improve the teaching profession (Martin, 1994).

Yashpal Committee (1993): It highlighted that inadequate teacher preparation programmes result in poor quality of education in schools. Therefore, the B.Ed. programme should offer the possibility of specialisation in secondary or elementary or nursery education. The duration of the programme should either be 1 year after graduation or 4 years after higher secondary. The contents of the programme should be reconstructed to ensure its relevance to the changing need school education (Mandal et al., 2017).

Analysis of O₂: To establish the relation between various aspects of teacher education in the 20th century of India.

RQ₂: How to establish the relation between various aspects of teacher education in the 20th century of India?

Nature of Teacher Education

The nature of teacher education was discussed below:

- The pre-service and in-service components of teacher education complement each other as a continuous process (Dwivedi, 2012).
- It is broad, comprehensive, ever evolving, and dynamic. In order to prepare teachers who are competent to face the challenges of the dynamic society (Sharma, 2004).
- The teacher education process is fully at the forefront of its curriculum, design, structure, and transaction modes (Kumar & Vashisth, 2014).
- This system is associated with the interdependence of inputs, processes, and outputs.

Importance of Teacher Education

Educating a boy affects an individual, educating a girl affects the whole family and educating a teacher affects the whole community. The importance of teacher education was as followed:

- Develop learners' perceptions, motivations, build self-confidence, raise awareness, and develop a favourable attitude (Dwivedi, 2012).
- Using methodology of teaching and creating social insight.
- Teacher education is one of the hallmarks of the modern education and school organisation (Anshuman, 2024).
- Improving standards and training for democracy.
- Through this process, recent developments are reasonably raised through teacher education interaction (Paul & Chatterjee, 2023).

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- As a lifelong learner, the teacher always keeps himself updated by example to keep his image to the learners (Ronfeldt, Farmer, Mc Queen, & Grissom, 2015).

Challenges in Teacher Education

The challenges that teacher education faces, were discussed below:

- At present, the different types of teacher education institutions lack adequate infrastructure and modernisation (Mishra, 2020).
- Teacher education colleges have unhealthy financial status and inadequate resources that are too low (Desai, 2012).
- Appointment of ineligible teachers in private teacher training institutes, opacity of the student enrolment process and admission of low quality students have resulted in poor quality learners (Bhatia et al., 2024).
- Traditional curriculum, methods of teaching, haphazard, improper organisation, unplanned, and insufficient co-curricular activities in the teacher education programme (Goel, 2012).
- Lack of proper time tables in the teacher training programme (Dwivedi, 2012).
- Lacking in feedback mechanism.
- The negative attitude of managements towards the development of material resources (Gupta, 1999).
- Weakness in understanding the purpose of teacher education (Paul & Chatterjee, 2023).
- Secondary level teacher education cannot be the sole standard of higher education.
- There is a considerable lack of teachers' responsibility and student-teacher commitment to the profession (Desai, 2012).

Suggestions for the Challenges of Teacher Education

Some suggestions for the challenges of teacher education were discussed below:

- Enhance the institutional capacity available at present for ensuring the adequate supply of trained teachers for all levels of school education (Aggarwal, 1996).
- Potentially employing all types of organisations that are required to train all levels of existing cadre services (Anshuman, 2024).
- Coordination between the institutional structures operating at different levels is urgently needed (Paul & Chatterjee, 2023).
- The teacher education process needs to be strengthened by the communication, collaboration, and coordination between different institutions (Rakes, Fields, & Cox, 2006).
- Imagine an innovative and comprehensive model of teacher education (Balwaria, & Gupta, 2014).
- Developing a curriculum policy and framework for teacher education that is compatible with NCTE (NCTE, 1998).
- The Central Government mainly provides comprehensive policies and legal frameworks on teacher education, and the State Government is implementing various aspects, and both the Governments need to give greater importance and focus on various activities related to teacher education (Anshuman, 2024).
- For pre-service training, the Government and Government aided teachers' education institutions are financial supported by the respective State Government and for in-service training, financial support is largely provided by the Central Government (Vashist, 2003).

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- The privatisation of teacher education should be regulated and affiliation condition should be made strict.
- The practicing schools have to be taken into confidence. To achieve this, teachers in teachers' colleges need to maintain close ties with schools. Curriculum and hands-on experiences, including practice teaching, can be effectively adjusted to positively impact school practices (Aggarwal, 1996).
- Teacher educators must be proficient and experienced in language skills (Balwaria, & Gupta, 2014).
- The curriculum of the teacher education system needs to be modified as the society changes.
- For the development of the profession, educators should from time to time have arrangements for various seminars, summer institutes, and research symposiums (Anshuman, 2024).
- It is important for teachers to make the right decisions through discussion and to have a positive relationship with each other (Dodiya, 2018).
- The teacher pupil ratio must be ideally 1:8.
- Internship in teacher education should be objective, reliable, and valid (Sharma, 2013).

CONCLUSION

Special knowledge, skills, and behaviours are developed through teaching as a professional activity. Teacher competence and performance serve as one of the most important criteria for professionalism in school and society. Through interpersonal communication, empowerment, and organisational leadership, the skills of the teacher are determined (Dexter, Anderson, & Becker, 1999). The goal should be to better educate skilled teachers in the interests of children and society, especially to uncover aspects of fancy (Goel, 2012). Teacher educators should be taught the value of proper training in the teacher education system. There is a need for teacher education to develop a particular aspect of society and develop a positive attitude towards the profession (Balwaria & Gupta, 2014). Teacher education was particularly seen in the development of quantitative and qualitative aspects. All the above-described commissions, committees, reports, schemes, programmes, and activities in the 20th century of India, emphasis on the quality of teachers in general and teacher educator in specific. At present, teachers are displaying more knowledge in the way teachers are communicating information. The existing teachers' training institutions of the state has yet lot to do for teachers in order to articulate innovations in terms of approach pedagogy for qualitative improvement of school education so, that they can response to the various demands of the students community.

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Conflict of Interest

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